

SafeCREW GUIDELINE #4

WATER MANAGEMENT TOOL FOR DBP MINIMIZATION IN DWDN

Figure 1 Water management tool scheme

Introduction

Access to safe drinking water is essential, but disinfection can generate potentially harmful disinfection by-products (DBPs). Compounds such as trihalomethanes (THMs) and haloacetic acids (HAAs) are common and regulated, while others, more toxic, occur at lower concentrations. The formation and fate of DBPs in drinking water distribution networks (DWDNs) depend on multiple factors, including disinfectant type and dose, source water quality, natural organic matter characteristics, inorganic species (e.g., bromide), hydraulic residence time, and operational conditions. This guideline presents a water management tool to estimate DBP concentrations along the network and assess associated health risks using online data and predictive models. When implemented as a decision support system, the tool can also provide operational recommendations for both the drinking water treatment plant (DWTP) and DWDN. Figure 1 shows the information fluxes in the water management tool.

Target Audience

These guidelines are intended for water utilities managing DWTPs and DWDNs, or distribution networks alone, that aim to enhance their water quality control systems by leveraging online data and DBP predictive models.

Scope and Objectives

This document provides fundamental concepts for implementing a risk-based management approach in drinking water distribution networks (DWDNs), as well as the minimum requirements for the effective use of the proposed water management tool. It also introduces a web-based application (DBP Risk Explorer) developed to enable utilities to generate preliminary estimates of DBP concentrations and associated risk levels throughout the distribution network. This document summarizes part of *Deliverable D3.3 Guideline for monitoring water quality and management of disinfection by-products in drinking water distribution networks*.

- Describe the water management tool and the requirements for implementation
- Illustrate its implementation through a case study
- Present the DBP Risk Explorer web-based application

Guideline

1) Description of the water management tool

It is specially developed for networks using sodium hypochlorite as disinfectant. The overall structure of the tool is illustrated in Figure 1. The tool is fed with online data from sensors in the DWTP and the DWDN, including water temperature, chlorine doses, free chlorine concentration, flow rates, tank volumes, valve status, and other water quality parameters.

This data is used to estimate free chlorine and DBP concentrations (THMs, HAAs, haloacetonitriles (HANs) and chlorate) at all points in the network using the mathematical models developed in SafeCREW (see Deliverable D3.2). Based on these estimates, a risk assessment is performed, and a risk index is calculated for each point of the network. For this, a new risk indicator (normalized risk index, NRI) was developed that is more intuitive than conventional cancer risk indexes. This indicator ranges from 0 to 1 (representing no cancer risk and the maximum acceptable regulatory risk, respectively), making it easy to interpret (see Deliverable D3.3 for more details on calculations).

Finally, recommendations based on the predicted concentrations and associated risks are generated to support decision-making at both plant and network levels, with the goal of complying with regulatory limits and reducing health risks associated with DBPs.

2) Requirements for the implementation of the water management tool

The implementation of the proposed water management tool requires several key elements: the availability of online monitoring systems (e.g., flow, tank levels, chlorine, and optionally DBPs), a calibrated hydraulic model of the distribution network suitable for simulation (e.g., using EPANET), and targeted sampling campaigns to measure DBPs across the network. These data are essential to calibrate and support accurate water quality modelling and risk assessment.

3) Example of implementation

This tool was developed specifically for case study #3 (Tarragona, Spain) and implemented offline. Figure 2 shows the calculated risk for different points of the network in a specific period as an example of the output of the tool.

Figure 2 Normalized Risk Index (NRI) for THMs and HAAs at different points within a DWDN, as an example of the implementation of the water management tool.

4) Web-based application

Building on the developments carried out for the creation of the water management tool, an online web-based application is available for utilities to generate preliminary estimations of DBP concentrations (THMs, HAAs, HANs, and chlorate) and the associated risk levels throughout the distribution network. This tool is designed as an initial decision-support resource, allowing users to visualize and assess potential water quality issues in a simplified and accessible environment. The website is open and available on [DBP Risk Explorer](#).

Figure 3 Initial screen of DBP Risk Explorer (left) and output of one simulation for THMs (right)

Conclusion

The developed water management tool supports proactive management for utilities. By integrating modelling and risk assessment, it enables estimation of DBPs and associated risks across the network using an intuitive normalized risk index. It was demonstrated in case study Tarragona. The proposed approach enables a shift to risk management. It supports utilities in moving beyond compliance towards proactive control aligned with EU objectives. Deliverable D3.2 and Deliverable D3.3 give further details about the DBP prediction models and the tool itself, respectively.

References

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